

Right-Libertarian Theory of History. Part III: The Libertarian Capitalist Government

Libertarian Hermit

Abstract

The property rights are the determining factor in economic relations. However, they are also the effect of a preceding factor: the form of government. Thus, depending on the government, there will be a tendency toward private or collective ownership. In the case of a monarchy, this form of government determines a tendency toward private property; on the contrary, democracy tends toward the collectivization of property. In this sense, for a libertarian capitalist society to be feasible, its form of government must be an aristocratic democracy; that is, a democracy in which only those who own property can participate. Finally, it is demonstrated that a libertarian capitalist society is a society of shareholders governed by a CEO. In other words, a libertarian capitalist society coincides with what Mencius Moldbug called “joint-stock republic”.

Keywords: Monarchy, Democracy, Aristocratic Democracy, Libertarian Capitalist Government, Society of Shareholders, Joint-Stock Republic.

The form of government as the cause of property rights

While it is true that property rights determine the type of economy of a society, where capitalism is the effect of private property and communism of collective property rights, property rights themselves are the effect of a prior and primary cause: the system of government, that is, the way in which society is governed by a political authority. Thus, the political power of the government can be distributed in three possible forms: monarchy, aristocracy, and democracy. This categorization is not arbitrary but is based on the logical structure of the distribution of political power. If political power is held by a single person, the system of government is called a “monarchy”; if political power is distributed among a few individuals, it is called an aristocracy; finally, if political power is distributed equally among all members of society, the system of government is a democracy (Polybius, *Histories*, VI, 3, 3-4. 1; Cicero, *Republic*, I, 42). In that sense, depending on the type of government, there is a tendency towards certain forms of property distribution, so the property rights would be its immediate effect.

The monarchy, which is the first case, where political power resides with the king, implies that ownership of all the territory he governs belongs to him. The king is the sole owner of the land, and all his subjects are subject to his power as tenants. And although free market economic can be established in a monarchical government, absolute ownership of the land belongs to the monarch. As Hans-Hermann Hoppe argued, monarchy implies the private ownership of the government: “Having to begin small, the original form of government is typically that of personal rule: of private ownership of the governmental apparatus of compulsion (monarchy)” (Hoppe, 2007: 16). Consequently, it can be inferred that the historical emergence of the state is directly related to the establishment of the monarchy, since both the state and the king, as absolute owners of the land, have the right to treat all their subjects as tenants on their domains. Therefore, taxes are nothing more than the rent, tolls, and fees that these subjects must pay to carry out their economic activities. In other words, the state and the king are both landowners who administer their territory.

To better understand the equivalence between the state and the monarchy, it is necessary to consider the government structure of the Neo-Assyrian Empire, which developed between the tenth and sixth centuries B.C. At that time, the Assyrian king possessed absolute power over his domains, as he was the sole landowner, which allowed him to intervene in the economy:

“The Assyrian king enjoyed absolute power over the state, there being only three checks to his autocratic rule, religion, legal precedent, and the temper of his nobles and officials. (...) Finally, even the economy was subject to his will, for in theory he owned all the land, and trade, both domestic and foreign, depended upon his sanction” (Grayson, 2006: 196).

Thus, as the absolute owner of the government, the king has the right to grant tax exemptions and economic benefits to anyone he considers suitable according to his interests, and therefore he will tend to intervene in the free market economy through protectionist measures such as monopolies.¹ Furthermore, these privileges will tend to be inherited, so monarchy inevitably creates the conditions for the formation of a legally protected aristocratic caste, which represents a further obstacle to the free market. All this can be inferred from the following statement by Hoppe:

“In the case of government, this exclusive character of private property takes on a special meaning. In this case it implies that everyone but the ruler and his family is excluded from benefiting from nonproductively acquired property and income. Only the ruling family—and to a minor extent its friends, employees, and business partners—shares in the enjoyment of tax revenues and can lead a parasitic life” (Hoppe, 2007: 21).

Hoppe’s reference to the parasitic nature of the way in which the king and his family acquire their wealth is only explained under the condition that the king is a landowner, and not a capitalist entrepreneur. The king acquires his wealth from the rent he charges his subjects, which he collects

¹ Monopoly is not an inherent condition of the free market, but rather an economic privilege that the state guarantees to certain companies so that they are protected from commercial competition. Rothbard briefly summarizes the legal status of the monopoly: “The only viable definition of monopoly is a grant of privilege from the government” (Rothbard, 1977: 60).

in the form of taxes. Thus, taxes in a monarchy are justified by the absolute right of private property that the king has over the government and the land. However, subjects cannot acquire absolute private property, which means they cannot change their status as tenants. However, monarchy is not only the negation of private property in individuals, but the same is also true at its other extreme: democracy.

Unlike a monarchy, democracy is the form of government in which all individuals in society possess equal political power. In other words, democracy is an equal distribution of political power. This implies that the political authority of a democratic regime inevitably tends toward the continuous redistribution of wealth to the benefit of the poorest. For this to be possible, a democratic government is obliged to expropriate some of the wealth of the richest to make redistribution effective. Therefore, the political equality of democracy determines an egalitarian economy; that is, democracy creates legal conditions for the establishment of collective property rights, which is the basis of communism. The causal relationship between democracy and communism was deduced by both liberal and Marxists intellectuals. On the one hand, Alexis de Tocqueville inferred that universal democracy inevitably tends toward social justice and the redistribution of wealth:

“Democratic laws generally tend to promote the welfare of the greatest possible number; for they emanate from a majority of the citizens, who are subject to error, but who cannot have an interest opposed to their own advantage” (Tocqueville, 1847: 258).

On the other hand, within the domain of Marxist theory, there is the causal inference deduced by Karl Kautsky, who postulated that democracy is the necessary means for the collectivization of the means of production, that is, democracy is essential for the establishment of socialism:

“Democracy is the essential basis for building up a Socialist system of production. Only under the influence of democracy does the proletariat attain that maturity which it needs to be able to bring about Socialism, and democracy supplies the surest means for testing its maturity” (Kautsky, 1981: 42).

The democratic participation of individuals through universal suffrage enables the political organization of socialists, through political parties, to gain power peacefully. Thus, by achieving an absolute majority in parliament and the executive branch, they can legitimately proceed to expropriate the means of production to legally establish communism through legal reforms. This causal link between democracy and socialism allowed Kautsky to understand that democracy is the precondition for socialism, implying that democracy originates in a political context prior to socialism:

“No socialism without democracy. But this proposition is not equally true if reversed. Democracy is quite possible without Socialism. A pure democracy is even conceivable apart from Socialism (...) In any case, it may be said that democracy is possible without Socialism, and precedes it” (Kautsky, 1981: 7).

In this sense, the fact that democracy causally precedes socialism means that socialism is not its inevitable consequence, but rather that democracy can condition the existence of redistributive capitalist economic systems that can counteract the tendency toward communism. For instance, the welfare state is a capitalist economic model in which the state intervenes in the economy to ensure social justice and the redistribution of wealth to the most vulnerable social classes in society. As Marx and Engels argued, these redistributive policies within capitalism correspond to bourgeois socialism (Marx and Engels, 1976: 513). However, the inevitable tendency of universal suffrage democracy towards socialism is not recent; this causal relationship was first deduced by Aristotle who argued that democracy is the regime of government in which political authority represents the interests of those who have the least property in society, that is, all those who belong to the poorest class: “A democracy is the opposite; those who do not possess much property, and are poor, are in authority” (Aristotle, *Politics*, III, 8, 1279b15).

Thus, Aristotle concluded that, with a democratic authority in government, its dependence on the popular will, dominated by the poor classes, will tend to satisfy the demands of the latter through the redistribution of wealth in society, which implies the inevitable expropriation of property from the rich:

“For popular leaders sometimes treat the notables unjustly in order to curry favor with the people and force them to combine, by redistributing their properties or their income by means of PUBLIC SERVICES; and sometimes they bring slanderous accusations against the rich so as to be in a position to confiscate their property” (Aristotle, *Politics*, V, 5, 1305a5).

Thus, Aristotle already demonstrated that universal democracy creates the legal conditions for the economic transition to communism. In that sense, if democracy is the inherent form of government of communism; while, at other extreme, monarchy is the inherent form of government of monopoly capitalism, which form of government inevitably establishes the legal conditions for a libertarian free market? The answer is simple: aristocratic government. However, it is necessary to modify its meaning in relation to Aristotle’s definition of aristocracy. For Aristotle, aristocracy is not based on wealth, but on the virtue or merit of the individual. In the case where wealth is prerequisite for governing, Aristotle defined that type of government as oligarchy: “Aristocracy is held most of all to exist when offices are distributed on the basis of virtue. For virtue is the defining mark of aristocracy, wealth of oligarchy (...)” (Aristotle, *Politics*, IV, 8, 1294a10).

The problem with the distinction that Aristotle made between aristocracy and oligarchy is that the latter is a deviation or degeneration of the former; that is, oligarchy is the corrupt form of government of the aristocracy: “Deviations from these (...) oligarchy from aristocracy (...)” (Aristotle, *Politics* III, 7, 1279b5). Polybius also expressed the same idea: “Aristocracy by its very nature degenerates into oligarchy (...)” (Polybius, *Histories*, IV, 4, 2-12). However, in a libertarian society, virtue or merit is intrinsically linked to wealth; that is, the greater the accumulated wealth, the greater the individual’s virtue. This is because the prosperity an individual achieves in the free market is a consequence of their intelligence, discipline, and perseverance in the face of the

inherent difficulties of managing and expanding a business with no help other than their own strength. This does not hold true for entrepreneurs who prosper with state support, where tax exemptions and monopolies are the true cause of their prosperity.

The libertarian capitalist government

In a libertarian capitalist society, the wealthiest are those who possess the most merit, and therefore virtue; whereas in a capitalist society with state protection, the most prosperous are not the most virtuous, since their wealth would be less in an absolute free market economy. Furthermore, the existence of monopolies and cartels of private companies protected by the state leads to the formation of an artificial commercial aristocracy that is not a consequence of the free market. Therefore, to ensure their economic power, they will always demand that the state protect their legal privileges, which only serves to distort the free market. The state and the free market are incompatible. If the state is itself an obstacle to the realization of a fully free market, what form of government should a libertarian society adopt so that the free market can exist without any restrictions? A government in which the aristocracy democratically elects the political authority, that is, an aristocratic democracy.

Nevertheless, the democratic system of libertarian capitalist government is different from that of universal suffrage. First, only those who own property, whether real estate or shares, have the right to vote. This is because in a society founded on private property, those who do not own property cannot participate in political power. Otherwise, what inevitably occurs in universal suffrage democracies will happen: the tendency toward social justice and wealth redistribution—in other words, socialism. Secondly, in an aristocratic democracy, voting power is not equal among property owners. The value of a vote must be equivalent to the total wealth held by each owner relative to the total value of assets in the libertarian capitalist republic. This means that the political power of each individual varies according to changes in their wealth. Thus, if an individual's accumulated capital, including real estate and stocks in companies or corporations, represents 5% of the republic's total assets, their vote will be equivalent to 5% of the total vote in an election.

Therefore, an individual's political power will increase or decrease according to the percentage change in their wealth relative to the total assets of the libertarian capitalist republic. Thus, the inequality of political power among individuals is a consequence of economic inequality. In this sense, Ludwig von Mises demonstrated that in the market, when consumers acquire a good, it implies the democratic participation of individuals, since each one chooses according to their own interests. However, this democratic participation of consumers is unequal, since the vote of individuals with greater purchasing power in the market has a higher value than that of those with less purchasing power:

“It is true, in the market the various consumers have not the same voting right. The rich cast more votes than the poorer citizens. But this inequality is itself the outcome of a previous voting process.

To be rich, in a pure market economy, is the outcome of success in filling best the demands of the consumers. A wealthy man can preserve his wealth only by continuing to serve the consumers in the most efficient way” (Mises, 1998: 272).

Mises’ analysis coincides with the inherent democratic system of libertarian capitalist government: aristocratic democracy. Furthermore, it demonstrates that it is not unfair for the value of an individual’s vote in the election of the authority of the libertarian government to be related to the percentage of wealth they possess in relation to the total assets of society, because their wealth is a consequence of the high preference that consumers give to the goods and services they offer in the market. In other words, those with the greatest political power in a libertarian capitalist society are those who best satisfy consumer needs. Therefore, it is fair that those who possess the most wealth should also have the greatest political power. To better understand the aristocratic democratic system of libertarian capitalist government, the model of governance is identical to that of large corporations, where the chief executive officer or CEO is elected by the shareholders. This implies that libertarian capitalist society is not a civil society, but a shareholder society.

But what kind of society is a society formed exclusively by shareholders? Libertarian capitalist society coincides with what Mencius Moldbug called “joint-stock republic”:

“The joint-stock republic is a very different entity from your ordinary, democratic republic. Its shares are negotiable and freely traded. Owning a share is not a “right”, except in the sense that if you own a share of Intel you have a right to receive Intel dividends. And, most importantly, the republic is operated for the exclusive benefit of its shareholders. All corporate governance mechanisms are otherwise the same, although without a superior sovereign to enforce them they must enforce themselves” (Moldbug, 2009: 74).

The legal basis that justifies the need for the libertarian capitalist government to be a joint-stock republic is that public law is subordinated to private law. Since the state does not exist, legal relations between individuals are built on private law, so private property is what conditions all public relations between individuals. Consequently, the constitution and legal code of the joint-stock republic are established according to the dictates of the political authority governing the republic, which represents the interests of all shareholders of the joint-stock republic. Thus, the political authority of joint-stock republic is exercised by a CEO who concentrates all political control of the republic. In this sense, it is not necessary for political power to be divided into several branches as in the case of democratic states, since the CEO of the joint-stock republic is overseen by the board of director, who represent the interests of the shareholders. This establishes a balance of power between the CEO and the shareholders.

Regarding the selection of the CEO, the election must, of course, be organized by the general meeting of shareholders of the joint-stock republic. In other words, the libertarian capitalist is a large business corporation that arises from the voluntary association of shareholders. Therefore, the CEO of the joint-stock republic is only accountable to the general meeting of shareholders. And this must be the case, since the CEO must manage in the best interests of the joint-stock

republic's shareholders, as they are the owners of the republic. The joint-stock republic is, in essence, a private ownership government. In this sense, any attempt to justify the claim that the CEO must also serve the interests of employees, consumers, bondholders, and creditors—that is, the entire set of stakeholders—implies a violation of private property rights. Therefore, requiring a corporation to serve the interests of its stakeholders is nothing more than a socialist policy of redistribution and expropriation of wealth within the business sphere. Milton Friedman denounced this implicit consequence of the stakeholder-based business model:

“But the doctrine of ‘social responsibility’ taken seriously would extend the scope of the political mechanism to every human activity. It does not differ in philosophy from the most explicitly collectivist doctrine” (Friedman, 2007: 178).

Thus, stakeholder-focused business policies are socialism. As E. Merrick Dodd rightly argued, private enterprise produces for the exclusive benefit of its shareholders, who are its owners: “The business is still a private enterprise existing for the profit of its owners, who are now the stockholders” (Dodd, 1932: 1146).

Finally, the legal structure of a libertarian capitalist government must necessarily centralize all the legal laws of the joint-stock republic into a single, unified legal code for all members of society. The existence of different legal codes implies the overlapping of laws, which would cause constant conflict among individuals. Therefore, the legal system must be universal for everyone, just as a unified monetary system is essential, since multiple currencies hinder trades. Similarly, the existence of diverse legal codes within the same jurisdiction would prevent individuals from having a common legal framework for resolving their disputes. While David Friedman argued that in a libertarian capitalist society legal laws are produced in the market (Friedman, 2014: 113), this assertion is contradictory, since any court with its own legal code will enter into jurisdictional conflict with other courts, because different sanctions will exist for the same crime, which would de facto imply the annulment of equality before the law.

In that sense, Tyler Cowen was right to state that Friedman's position is inconsistent, since a libertarian capitalist society is only stable if it has a single legal code: “Instead, the argument is that Friedman's scenario is not an independent alternative. Competing law codes are stable only if they evolve into a dominant agency or arbitration network (...)” (Cowen, 1992: 255). And Cowen was not wrong in inferring that the existence of multiple legal codes would unleash a war of all against all: “Competing law codes do not prove feasible, as libertarian anarchy collapses into Hobbesian anarchy” (Cowen, 1992: 255). But to settle this discussion once and for all, the existence of a single legal code is demonstrated by the advantages of a single legal tender: it allows the competing interests of individuals to converge towards a common interest that benefits both. Furthermore, the existence of a single legal code, established by the CEO of the joint-stock republic, allows all courts to compete fairly in the market, as consumers will hire the services that best suit their purchasing power without worrying if the court has a less fair code than its rivals.

On the other hand, judges and will compete in the market to determine who can best interpret the law at the lowest possible cost, without any conflict arising from overlapping jurisdictions between the courts. They will also only need to master a single legal code, avoiding the burden of multiple laws that would result from having more than one legal code for the same crime. Thus, the joint-stock republic would ensure its political unity. Furthermore, it is undeniable that a company, firm, or corporation cannot function properly if it has multiple, contradictory regulatory systems. For management to effectively run a company, unity of command can only be exercised if the rules are governed by a single code.

Conclusion

Forms of government are not simply structures for administering power; they are the causal factor that determines how property is distributed. Thus, a democratic society will tend to collectivize private property and therefore will always tend toward socialism. Conversely, a monarchical government will tend toward the privatization of collective property, essentially as the private property of the king. Similarly, in the transition from a monarchical to a democratic regime, the king's private property is transformed into public property. Therefore, Hoppe's deduction regarding monarchy as the most suitable form of state government for the free market is correct. The same applies to his deduction regarding the tendency of democratic states toward socialism, in which the decivilizing process intensifies (Hoppe, 2007: 17). However, in the case of libertarian capitalist society, neither monarchy nor democracy is suitable for its government structure based on association of owners or shareholders. The libertarian capitalist government, or joint-stock republic, is a form of government in which no shareholder can secure long-term influence in government.

If their businesses fail, the decline in their assets directly impacts in their political power. Therefore, the distribution of political power among the shareholders of the joint-stock republic reflects the balance of power that exists in the free market. Furthermore, this aspect of the aristocratic democracy of the joint-stock republic implies absolute social mobility. This means that a simple, propertyless worker, if they manage and invest their wealth wisely, found a company, and acquire property, can obtain the right to vote by automatically becoming a shareholder of the joint-stock republic. Conversely, if a prominent entrepreneur loses all their assets due to poor decisions, this politically implies the loss of their voting rights, as they cease to be a shareholder of the joint-stock republic. Ultimately, the aristocracy of the joint-stock republic is based exclusively on the meritocracy of the free market.

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